

ABRASIVE WEAR MECHANISM*Agazade N.**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
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PhD scholar***ABSTRACT**

Wear - is a change in the size, shape, mass or condition of the surface of a product or structure due to destruction (wear) of the surface layer. Abrasive wear is the destruction of the surface by hard abrasive grains. There are two possible types of impact of abrasive grains on the surface.

Hydrabrasive wear change the size, shape, mass or condition of the surface of a material under the influence of a moving liquid with inclusions of solid matter distributed throughout its volume. The intensity of hydroabrasive wear depends on the quality of the wear material, size, shape, hardness, density of solid particles of the hydraulic mixture, its concentration, density, viscosity, corrosiveness of the liquid medium, speed of movement of particles relative to the wear surface, angle of approach to the surface, etc.

Keywords: wear, abrasive wear, fatigue wear, hydroabrasive wear, erosion wear, deformation, choke valve needle failures.

Introduction.

Iron is widely used in various fields of human activity. Even with the advent of other structural materials, it has not lost its relevance and demand in industry, construction and other sectors. But negative environmental factors and aggressive environments can affect the condition of metal structures. This necessitates the search for solutions that provide reliable protection of metal from destruction, abrasive wear and corrosion. This wear of the material is associated with the impact of hard particles on the surface, which cut and scratch the surface. This leads to the fact that metal structures lose their operational properties. The initial type of abrasive wear is the formation of notches and scratches on the metal surface. The space between the contact zone of the elements gradually expands, noise and vibration appear in the operation of the equipment.

Basic concepts.

Solid particles leave small dents on the surface, mineral substances with sharp edges leave cutting marks. When exposed to other factors, grooves or holes remain on the surface. In some cases, under the influence of other abrasive substances, the roughness can be smoothed out.

The corrosion resistance of the material depends on the level of homogeneity. The more uniform it is, the more resistant to rust. Various contaminants, unevenness, roughness and abrasions act as an electrolyte that collects moisture on the surface of a metal structure. They lead to the development of corrosion, which intensifies at high ambient temperatures, dust, humidity, and the presence of aggressive substances in the air. To determine methods of metal protection, environmental humidity and the mode of use of structures are taken into account. The rate of deformation of a metal surface also depends on the direction of attack. The smaller the angle of attack, the less intense the shock impulses transmitted to the surface from the particle. As the ambient temperature rises and the presence of aggressive substances in the air, the rate of destruction increases. Damage in the surface layers of the material contributes to the appearance of stress, which causes deformation in the form of cracks and corrosion. In

fuel, pumping, and plumbing equipment, metal wear is determined by the quality and composition of the liquids used. Water, oil, lubricants, fuel, brake and other fluids contain fine particles of quartz, mineral fragments, metal oxides, potassium and calcium salts, sand, etc. When moving liquids, they contribute to abrasive wear of transport communications.

Setting the issue.

Solid fractions have different shapes and orientations relative to surfaces. Minerals with sharp edges and edges leave cutting marks, while others cause plastic deformation in the form of grooves or holes. The roughness can subsequently be partially removed with other abrasives. In some cases, particles of less hardness are pressed into the surface layers, gradually contributing to loosening of the structure. The opposite effect is also possible: hardening of the deformable layer by cold hardening. The more homogeneous the metal, the better it resists corrosion. Surface contamination, unevenness, scratches and cracks increase the amount of adsorbed moisture, which serves as an electrolyte. This leads to the development of corrosion, and its intensification is facilitated by increased environmental temperature, dust, air humidity, and exposure to aggressive gases. The impact of abrasives moving in a fluid flow is typical for plumbing, pumping and fuel equipment. For example, parts of energy centrifugal pumps are especially affected by fine fractions. Crude oil contains quartz, plagioclase, and mineral rock fragments. Tap water contains metal oxides, magnesium and calcium salts. When extracted from wells – sand, various minerals. The carriers of abrasives are lubricants, fuel, brake and working fluids.

Fan blades, pumps for pumping out contaminated gases, blast furnaces, and parts of solid fuel engines are susceptible to this type of destruction. The most common phenomenon of gas abrasive wear is the effect of road dust on the car body. 70-90% of it consists of abrasion products from pads, tires, and road surfaces.

Solution method.

Abrasive deformation is one of the fastest destruction processes. To prevent emergency situations, enterprises create funds that ensure timely replacement and

repair of material and technical base. To reduce the rate of destruction, the hardness of the working surfaces should be 1.3 times higher than abrasives. This ratio is considered optimal from an economic and technical point of view. Further increase in strength characteristics does not produce a noticeable effect. Ways to increase resistance to abrasive wear of metals and alloys:

1. Galvanic coating: chrome, nickel;
2. Anodizing: formation of solid oxide;
3. Nitriding: saturation of surface layers with nitrogen;
4. Gumming: treatment with polyurethane.
5. Surface reinforcement by the laser technology.
6. Flame hardening method.

Flame hardening is one of the surface reinforcement methods. The essence of the surface hardening method with gas flame heating is to heat the surface of the product with an acetylene-oxygen flame, the tem-

perature of which will reach 3150 degrees. In approximately 10-15 seconds, the surface layer is heated to 1000-1300 degrees. The treatment makes it possible to obtain a hardened layer with a thickness of 1 to 10 mm, the hardness of which will be HRC 58-60.

The cooling medium used is: compressed air, water, emulsions and salt solutions. After hardening, low-temperature tempering is carried out under the influence of a temperature of 180-220 degrees. For flame heating, welding torches are used, to which slotted and multi-flame tips are attached.

By means of flame hardening method, surface can be hardened efficiently and without lots of economical issues.

Conclusion.

1. The characteristics of abrasive wear have been investigated and the application of appropriate methods depending on the effect of the chemical environment has been considered.

Fig.1. Deformation of the surface with different micro particles

Fig.2. Different types of wear and their impact mechanism

Fig.3. Flame hardening method

References

1. J.N. Aslanov, A.B. Sultanova, Z.S. Huseynli, F.F. Mustafayev, Determination of Radial Strains in Sealing Elements with Rubber Matrix Based on Fuzzy Sets, Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems, 2022, 362 LNNS, pp. 765–773.
2. J.N. Aslanov, A.S. Ahmadov, Z.E. Eyvazova, G.A. Hamidova, L.R. Ibayeva, Harmonic analysis of loading characteristics research of pump jack, International Journal on “Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering”. March 2023, issue 54, vol.15, number 1, pp.110-115.
3. J.N. Aslanov, K.S. Mammadov, Design and performance analysis of improved valve construction being used in oil and gas industry, International Journal on Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering, 2022, 14(2), pp. 98-103.
4. M.B. Babanli, R.K. Mekhtiyev, N.A. Gurbanov, J.N. Aslanov, Y.S. Tanriverdiev, Cracks in hybrid fiber metal laminated nanocomposites under uniaxial tension, Journal of Applied Mechanics and Technical Physics, 2022, 63(5), pp. 876–8837.
5. R.J.K. Wood, in Shreir's Corrosion, Corrosion in Liquids, Corrosion Evaluation, 2010, 20, pp. 1005-1050.
6. Catarina Valente, Teresa Leanor, Neeraj Sharma. Laser Cladding – A post processing technique for coating, repair and re-manufacturing. Journal of Materials Forming, Machining and Post Processing, 2020, pp. 231-249.
7. J.N. Aslanov, A.S. Ahmadov, Z.E. Eyvazova, G.A. Hamidova, L.R. Ibayeva, HARMONIC ANALYSIS OF LOADING CHARACTERISTICS RESEARCH OF PUMP JACK, International Journal on “Technical and Physical Problems of Engineering”. March 2023 Issue 54 Volume 15 Number 1 Pages 110-118.